

INTERFACIAL EFFECTS IN CORE–SHELL POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Effects of silica and titania nanoparticles of a wide range of size (8 – 80 nm in diameter for primary particles) and specific surface roughness (specific surface area, S_{BET} , 25 – 342 m²/g) on interfacial dynamics of linear polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) in nanocomposites (NCs) of the *core–shell* type were studied by employing differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermally stimulated depolarization currents (TSDC), and broadband dielectric relaxation spectroscopy (DRS). All techniques revealed an increase of the interfacial polymer fraction with increasing surface roughness and provided some evidence of increased density in the interfacial layer. These effects were accompanied by enhanced dynamics and cooperativity of the corresponding interfacial segmental relaxation (α_{int} relaxation). Results were critically compared with those of conventional NCs based on crosslinked PDMS filled with *in situ* generated small silica (~5 nm) and titania (~30 nm) nanoparticles. In both *core–shell* and conventional PDMS based NCs the segmental α relaxation was analyzed in terms of three contributions. In NCS based on a thermoplastic polymer (poly(L–lactic acid), PLLA) filled with nano–inclusions of various sizes and different dimensionality, on the contrary, only a single segmental α relaxation was observed and the dielectric strength was found to systematically decrease in the NCs in correlation to a decrease of the heat capacity change at glass transition.

1 INTRODUCTION

Interfacial effects are significant for understanding and rationalizing properties improvement in polymer nanocomposites (PNCs) [1]. The existence of an *interfacial polymer fraction* in PNCs [2, 3], characterized by a modified structure [4], slower dynamics [5–9] and increased thermal stability [10], as compared to the bulk, has been found to affect significantly or even dominate the properties of PNCs. Kumar and coworkers suggested that the interfacial layer thickness may decrease with curvature of the adsorbing surface [3] and increase with size of nanoparticles [11] and references therein. Stronger polymer–particle bonding has been suggested to be at the origin of the increased interfacial layer thickness and slower interfacial dynamics in polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) / titania as compared to PDMS / silica conventional PNCs [5, 6]. We have recently demonstrated similarities in the behavior of linear PDMS adsorbed on fumed silica particles in *core–shell* type PNCs [12, 13] with that of polymers adsorbed on flat solid surfaces [14, 15] and in conventional PNCs [6, 16]. The surface and porosity characteristics of fumed silicas are reflected in the specific surface area, S_{BET} [12, 13].

In the present study, we demonstrate results by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and two dielectric relaxation spectroscopy techniques (thermally stimulated depolarization currents, TSDC, and broadband dielectric spectroscopy, DRS), suggesting dependence of the characteristics of the interfacial polymer fraction and dynamics on nanofillers' surface characteristics, moreover, the

roughness (represented from S_{BET}). We study two series of PNCs samples, one based on the rubbery polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) and the other based on the thermoplastic poly(L-lactic acid (PLLA). Linear PDMS was adsorbed (via hydrogen bonding) on aggregates of fumed metal oxide particles of a wide range of S_{BET} . Results were compared with those of previous study on conventional NCs (and further analyzed here) based on crosslinked PDMS with *in situ* generated and dispersed small silica and titania nanoparticles [6, 8]. On the other hand, the thermoplastic PLLA was filled with mainly commercial nanosized inclusions (spherical-like nanoparticles, nanosheets [17], and nanotubes). Effects are discussed in terms of dynamics in the interfacial layer and evaluation of the interfacial polymer fraction. The interfacial polymer fraction (Rigid Amorphous Fraction, *RAF*) was evaluated in DSC by the deviation (missing part) of the heat capacity step of the nanocomposites (NCs) at glass transition, ΔC_p , from that of the neat polymer [2]. In DRS for oxide/rubber systems the segmental dynamics of the polymer at the interfaces was recorded as an additional relaxation mechanism (α_{int}) [6, 12, 13] and *RAF* was evaluated by comparing its dielectric strength ($\Delta\epsilon$) with that of the total segmental response (interfacial and bulk). On the other hand, for PLLA systems, *RAF* was estimated by the missing part from the $\Delta\epsilon$ of α (bulk) relaxation in the NCs from that of the neat polymer, the respective results being discussed within the final section of this article.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Materials

Main discussion here concerns materials based on linear PDMS ($MW \sim 2000$ and ~ 8000 , Kremniypolymer, Zaporozhye, Ukraine) adsorbed (via hydrogen bonding [5]) on aggregates of fumed metal oxide particles (pilot plant of the Institute of Surface Chemistry, Kalush, Ukraine) of a wide range of specific surface area (roughness), S_{BET} . The metal oxides used are titania (~ 70 nm in diameter for primary particles, ~ 800 nm in size for aggregates, $S_{BET} \sim 25$ m²/g) and various silicas (8–85 nm in diameter for primary particles, 300–600 nm in size for aggregates, $S_{BET} \sim 55$ –342 m²/g [12, 13, 18]). We refer to previous work for preparation of initial oxides and measurement of S_{BET} [18, 19] and of core-shell type PNCs [13]. We employ a critical comparison with results obtained in a previous study [6] on conventional NCs based on crosslinked PDMS ($MW \sim 18000$) with *in situ* generated and dispersed small silica (~ 5 nm in diameter) and titania (~ 30 nm in diameter) nanoparticles [20].

The second series of materials under investigation consists of poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA, Gorinchem, The Netherlands, $MW \sim 700$ kDa) filled with silica (12 nm in diameter, $S_{BET} \sim 200$ m²/g), Ag nanoparticles (40–90 nm in diameter, 10.5 g/cm³ in density), graphene oxide nanosheets (5 μ m in size, 1.5 nm in thickness, 1.85 g/cm³ in density), and multiwall carbon nanotubes (10–20 nm in diameter, 10 μ m in length, 2.1 g/cm³ in density) at relatively low contents (0.5–2.5 wt%). Fillers were dispersed in the PLLA matrix by means of properly prepared solutions and employing conventional mixing methods, both depending on the type of filler [17].

2.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Morphology was examined by field emission Scanning Electron Microscopy employing a QuantaTM 3D FEG (FEI Company, USA). The chamber operated at room temperature under high vacuum mode using an Everhart-Thornley Detector (ETD) at a voltage of 30 kV. A Helix detector operating at 15 kV was employed for liquid samples (i.e. samples containing 80 wt% PDMS).

2.3 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Thermal properties of the materials were investigated in helium / nitrogen atmosphere (for PDMS / PLLA based samples, respectively, due to different temperature ranges of measurements) in the overall temperature range from -180 to 200 °C using a TA Q200 series DSC instrument, calibrated with indium (for temperature and enthalpy) and sapphire (for heat capacity). Samples of ~ 8 mg in mass were closed in standard T-zero aluminium pans. Samples have been equilibrated in ambient conditions before measurements. After erasing thermal history of the materials at high temperatures (40 and 220 °C, for PDMS and PLLA based systems, respectively), samples were cooled down at ~ 100 K/min in order to suppress crystallization, and, finally, were heated at 10 K/min.

2.4 Thermally Stimulated Depolarization Currents (TSDC)

Thermally stimulated depolarization currents (TSDC) is a special dielectric technique in the temperature domain, characterized by high sensitivity and high resolving power, the latter arising from its low equivalent frequency (10^{-4} – 10^{-2} Hz) [21]. By this technique, the sample was inserted between the polished brass plates of a capacitor, placed in a Novocontrol TSDC sample cell and polarized by an electrostatic field E_p (~100 V/mm) at polarization temperature T_p (20 °C for PDMS based samples) for time $t_p = 5$ min. With the field still applied, the sample was cooled down to –150 °C (cooling rate 10 K/min, under nitrogen flow), sufficiently low to prevent depolarization by thermal energy, then short-circuited and reheated up to room temperature at a constant heating rate $b = 3$ K/min. Temperature control was achieved by means of a Novocontrol Quatro cryosystem. A discharge current was generated during heating and measured as a function of temperature with a sensitive programmable Keithley 617 electrometer.

2.5 Broadband Dielectric Relaxation Spectroscopy (DRS)

For dielectric relaxation spectroscopy (DRS) [22] measurements of PDMS based samples, the sample (same as that used for TSDC measurements) was placed between the plates of a capacitor and an alternate voltage was applied in a Novocontrol sample cell. The complex dielectric permittivity, $\epsilon^* = \epsilon' - i\epsilon''$, was recorded isothermally as a function of frequency in the range from 10^{-1} to 10^6 Hz at temperatures from –150 to 60 °C on heating (in nitrogen atmosphere) in steps of 2.5, 5 and 10 K (depending on the process under investigation) using a Novocontrol Alpha analyzer. The temperature was controlled to better than 0.5 K with a Novocontrol Quatro cryosystem. DRS measurements for PLLA based samples were performed isothermally at the selected temperature of 75 °C on initially amorphous samples.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 MATERIALS

Surface and porosity characteristics of the initial oxides have been studied previously employing isothermal Nitrogen adsorption–desorption techniques combined with Incremental Pores Size Distribution (IPSD) analysis [18]. The results suggest the formation of aggregates with initially non-porous particles that are characterized by textural porosity. Thus, S_{BET} values (25 – 342 m²/g) describe well the nanometric roughness at the external surfaces. Polymer adsorption results in gradual decrease of textural porosity (smoothing of surfaces). These changes can be followed for polymer loadings up to ~40 wt%, as at higher polymer loadings materials are in the liquid state rendering IPSD technique not applicable.

In the case of conventional NCs, IPSD analysis has not been performed, thus, the respective ‘accessible surface area’, S_{access} , of the spherical silica (5 nm) and titania (30 nm) nanoparticles was estimated via geometrical calculations and bibliographic values of the mass densities of the particles (2.65 and 4.23 g/cm³ for silica and titania, respectively [6]). According to these calculations, S_{access} is 453 m²/g for silica and 47 m²/g for titania. Employing similar calculations for the fillers dispersed in PLLA, we obtained S_{access} equal to 189 m²/g for silica, 721 m²/g for GO, 9 m²/g for Ag nanoparticles, and 127 m²/g for CNTs.

3.2 MORPHOLOGY

Figure 1 shows SEM images of the aggregates of nanooxides for gradually increasing PDMS loadings. One can clearly observe the nanoparticles of ~10–70 nm in diameter (Figure 1a,b) to form bunch-like aggregates varying between 250 nm and 1.5 μm in size (Figure 1c). The aggregates for samples of low S_{BET} are larger and better distributed in the polymer NCs, as compared to those of high S_{BET} , an interesting result with respect to processing and applications.

Figure 1: SEM images for the core–shell NCs (a) titania + 5 wt% PDMS, (b) silica + 40 wt% PDMS, and (c) silica + 80 wt% PDMS

3.3 GLASS TRANSITION

Figure 2 shows comparative DSC thermograms in the temperature region of glass transition for oxide/PDMS NCs and for comparison neat PDMS. The characteristic temperature T_g , determined as the midpoint of the heat capacity step at glass transition, is $-134\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for neat linear PDMS and $-128\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for neat crosslinked PDMS. T_g increases systematically and the glass transition step broadens in the presence of nanooxides. At the same time the heat capacity step, ΔC_p , reduces. These effects are uniquely affiliated to polymer–filler interactions, since crystallization was absent or extremely weak during cooling at high rate (not shown). As expected, the physical and spatial constraints imposed by the nanoparticles act as obstacles to polymer diffusion during glass transition [23].

Figure 2: Comparative DSC thermograms in the glass transition region of (a) core–shell and (b) conventional nanocomposites of metal oxide nanoparticles and PDMS

We should note that the interfacial polymer fraction, also called Rigid Amorphous Fraction (RAF), is thought to be completely immobile in DSC, making no contribution to the glass transition [2]. Thus, according to Wurm et al. [2] a ‘2–phase model’ can be applied to DSC results for the NCs for the quantitative estimation of RAF_{DSC} (Eq. 1). Results suggest increasing of RAF_{DSC} with filler fraction, as expected.

$$RAF_{DSC} = 1 - \frac{\Delta C_p^{NC}}{\Delta C_p^{polymer}} \quad (1)$$

3.4 SEGMENTAL DYNAMICS

3.4.1 Thermally Stimulated Depolarization Currents (TSDC)

TSDC thermograms for neat PDMS and selected silica/PDMS NCs are presented comparatively in Figure 3, in the temperature range between -140 and $-85\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The depolarization current density is normalized with the applied electric field [21], so that results for different samples can be compared to each other not only with respect to the temperature position of a peak (time scale of the corresponding relaxation), but also with respect to the magnitude of a peak (dielectric strength of the corresponding relaxation, $\Delta\epsilon$).

In the temperature range from -135 to -100 °C, i.e. in the range of the calorimetric glass transition (Figure 2), complex dispersions appear in the thermograms, consisting of up to three peaks for some NCs. The equivalent frequencies of TSDC and DSC measurements [21] are of similar range. According to respective studies on PDMS NCs [5, 8, 12, 13], the various relaxation peaks, called α_{bulk} , α_c and α_{int} in the order of increasing temperature in Figure 3, are dielectrically related with cooperative PDMS chain motions in the glass transition region. Additionally, Figure 3 illustrates the high resolving power of the TSDC technique, since it reveals several discrete relaxation processes, while in DSC measurements a single glass transition step is recorded (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Comparative TSDC spectra for core–shell (red triangles) and conventional (red cycles) silica / PDMS NCs and for comparison for neat PDMS (black symbols) in the temperature region of the glass transition. Arrows indicate the recorded dielectric relaxations related to glass transition.

The bulk segmental relaxation consists of two contributions, arising from extended amorphous regions (α_{bulk}) and from polymer chains restricted between condensed crystalline regions (α_c) [6]. Interestingly, TSDC was able to monitor the segmental mobility in the interfacial polymer layer [5, 6, 12, 13], i.e. the slower α_{int} process in Figure 3. The dynamics (time scale, strength and cooperativity) of the interfacial polymer relaxation, along with the bulk–like dynamics, will be evaluated and discussed in the following DRS section.

3.4.2 Broadband Dielectric Relaxation Spectroscopy (DRS)

DRS results focus again on segmental dynamics. DRS data recorded isothermally (section 2.5) have been replotted in Figure 4 as isochronal plots of the imaginary part of dielectric permittivity $\varepsilon''(T)$, in order to facilitate direct comparison with the DSC and TSDC thermograms of Figures 2 and 3, respectively. A relative to DSC high frequency of 3 kHz was selected to suppress effects of conductivity [22]. Additionally, DRS results were analyzed by fitting the Havriliak–Negami (HN) equation [22]

$$\varepsilon^*(f) = \frac{\Delta\varepsilon}{1 + if/f_0}^{\alpha_{HN}} \beta_{HN} \quad (2)$$

to the experimental data in order to evaluate the time scale (temperature dependence of the frequency maxima) (Figure 5a) and the dielectric strength, $\Delta\varepsilon$, (Figure 5b) of the various relaxations. In Eq. (2), f_0 is a characteristic frequency related to the frequency of maximum dielectric loss, and α_{HN} and β_{HN} are the shape parameters of the relaxation [22]. A sum of HN terms of the type (2), one for each of the relaxations (namely α_{bulk} , α_c and α_{int}), was fitted to the experimental data at each temperature and the fitting parameters were determined.

Figure 4: Comparative isochronal plots of the imaginary part of dielectric permittivity ε'' , replotted from DRS measurements at 3 kHz for (a) core-shell and (b) conventional silica / PDMS systems [6]. Indicated are the relaxation processes that represent segmental dynamics (dynamic glass transition). The arrows mark changes in interfacial polymer segmental dynamics (α_{int}) imposed by the increase of (a) S_{BET} and (b) filler fraction.

Figure 5: (a) Arrhenius plots and (b) dielectric strength vs reciprocal temperature for the segmental relaxations of bulk, bulk-like and interfacial polymer (α_{int}) and for the local relaxation of the $-OH$ groups at particle surfaces (S_{OH}). The lines in (a) are fittings of the VTFH and Arrhenius equations [5]. The lines (1) and (2) in both (a) and (b) correspond to the interfacial relaxation in conventional (1) PDMS/silica and (2) PDMS/titania nanocomposites [6]. Included in (a) are DSC and TSDC data [12]. The arrows mark changes imposed by the increasing of S_{BET} .

α_{bulk} is more clearly discerned for neat linear PDMS in Figure 4a, while α_c dominates the response of crosslinked PDMS in Figure 4b, as the degree of crystallinity, X_c , of this sample is quite high ($X_c \sim 0.8$ wt [6]). After analysis of the BDS spectra, we follow in Figure 5a that the time scale of these bulk-like relaxations remains almost unchanged with composition, while the dielectric strength of α_{bulk} decreases with both filler loading (Figure 4b) and S_{BET} (surface roughness) (Figure 5b).

In the intermediate temperature / frequency region between α_{bulk} and α_{int} processes in Figure 5a, the S_{OH} relaxation is also observed for some samples. S_{OH} , related to local motion of free hydroxyls on the oxide surface (Si-OH) [12], dominates the response of initial nanooxides (not shown) and is present here in the NCs of high surface area (Figure 5).

With both S_{BET} and filler loading increasing, α_{int} becomes faster (Figures 4a and 5a) and stronger (Figures 4b and 5b), respectively. In addition, α_{int} becomes more cooperative (higher fragility index m , details of calculation in Ref. [12]).

In addition to modification of dynamics at interfaces, the presence of the interfacial polymer leads to an increase of the internal polarization of the systems, in general. As an example, we show in Figure 6 isothermal plots of ε' at a very low temperature (-150 °C), where dipolar relaxation mechanisms

related to molecular motions (secondary polarization) do not contribute to the dielectric signal. At a fixed polymer loading of the NCs, ϵ' increases with S_{BET} beyond additivity (Figure 6a). Additionally, it is clear in Figure 6b that samples of 40 wt% PDMS demonstrate high values of ϵ' , while for higher polymer loadings ϵ' is strongly suppressed. We will provide an explanation for these findings later in terms of model that assumes the existence of specific conformations adopted by polymer chains at interfaces (insets to Figure 6b).

Figure 6: Changes of the real part of dielectric permittivity, ϵ' , at -150 °C against frequency imposed (a) by the adsorption of 40 wt% PDMS on silica (of high S_{BET}) and titania (low S_{BET}) and (b) by surface modification via zirconia nanoparticles grafting on silica of low S_{BET} and by the increase of the adsorbed polymer fraction (40 and 80 wt%) [13]. The insets show schematic models for the conformations of polymer chains at the interfaces.

Having firm evidence about the origin of the recorded segmental relaxations, we employ a model analogue to the one used previously for DSC (Eq. (1)) and calculate the interfacial PDMS fraction in the NCs, RAF_{DRS} , according to the following equation

$$RAF_{DRS} = \frac{\Delta\epsilon_{\alpha,int}}{\Delta\epsilon_{a,total}} = \frac{\Delta\epsilon_{\alpha,int}}{\Delta\epsilon_{a,bulk} + \Delta\epsilon_{\alpha,int}} \quad (3)$$

From the methodological point of view, Eq. (3) involves the total dielectric response of the segmental relaxations for each sample. Thus, we may assume that any systematic errors in the calculations and the comparison between different samples, arising from possible differences in polarizability of PDMS chains in the different fractions, are reduced by this calculation method. The suitability of Eq. (3) for calculating interfacial polymer fraction has been confirmed in NCs based on silica and various polymers [7, 9, 13]. Results for RAF_{DRS} are shown in Figure 7, for a selected temperature of -95 °C (as $\Delta\epsilon$ changes with temperature, Figure 5b). As expected, RAF_{DRS} increases systematically with filler fraction in Figure 7, the increase being stronger for silica/PDMS samples for both conventional and core-shell NCs. Figure 8 shows results for the dependence of RAF_{DRS} of core-shell NCs on S_{BET} , which suggest that, next to enhanced dynamics and cooperativity, RAF_{DRS} increases systematically with S_{BET} (surface roughness).

Figure 7: Interfacial polymer fraction against filler fraction for silica/PDMS (red symbols) and titania/PDMS (blue symbols) NCs of core-shell (circles) and conventional (triangles) type. The arrow marks the increasing of interfacial polymer fraction for the shorter PDMS chains.

Figure 8: (Left axis, circles) interfacial polymer fraction and (right axis, triangles) fragility index, m , of the interfacial relaxation (α_{int}) against surface roughness, S_{BET} , obtained by DRS at -95 °C for core-shell NCs

3.5 INTERPRETATIONS IN TERMS OF MODELS

The insets to Figures 6b and 8 show the simplified model employed for the interpretation of our results. According to this model, adsorption of PDMS proceeds via two chain conformations, which can be considered responsible for the molecular mobility recorded by DRS as interfacial α_{int} relaxation process: (a) extended tails forming the outer region, with bulk-like density but reduced mobility, and (b) flattened chains which form the inner quite dense region due to multiple contact points (loops) with the silica surface [14]. It has been also suggested that for low polymer contents the tails are mobile enough to cooperate with each other, but being sparsely distributed on the surfaces of the nanoparticles their cooperativity length (ζ) [24] is relatively large. Obviously, both types of conformations are characterized by increased orientation / order and polarizability and, this way, increase ε' , ε'' and $\Delta\varepsilon$ (Figures 5b and 6). In addition, increasing of S_{BET} leads to higher concentration of polymer-particle contact points and, therefore, to more dense interfacial layer. This implies reduction of the cooperativity length ζ at interfaces and, thus, in the frame of Adam-Gibbs theory [25], faster and more cooperative segmental dynamics, in agreement with results for α_{int} in the present work (Figure 5a). In the case of high polymer loadings, e.g. 80 wt% PDMS in Figure 6b, the additional polymer chains that connect to the additional contact points can form both extra tails and loops and, most probably, additional polymer layer(s). This implies serious obstacles to the orientation of the tails, resulting in reduction of dielectric response (ε' , in Figure 6b).

According to the above model, the main extracted result is the increase of the concentration of polymer-particle contact points with increasing of S_{BET} , in other words there should be an increase of the interfacial polymer density, ρ_{int} . We have employed the simple Eq. (4) for a rough estimation of the

apparent ρ_{int} (results not shown here). In Eq. (4) X_{PDMS} is the mass fraction of the polymer in the samples and l_{KS} is the length of *Kuhn segment* in a PDMS melt.

$$\rho_{int} = \frac{mass_{interfacial,PDMS}}{volume_{interfacial,PDMS}} = \frac{mass_{sample} \cdot X_{PDMS} \cdot RAF_{DRS}}{mass_{sample} \cdot (1 - X_{PDMS}) \cdot S_{BET} \cdot l_{KS}} \quad (4)$$

The results demonstrate the expected increase of apparent ρ_{int} with S_{BET} . At this point, we cannot conclude as to whether ρ_{int} is lower or higher comparing to that in bulk. Respective results in the literature are not clear. However, Polystyrene (PS) adsorbed on flat Si substrate shows higher density in the inner region of the interfacial layer than that in bulk, while the outer interfacial region is characterized by density equal to that in bulk [14]. Computer simulations on PS grafted on spherical nanoparticles demonstrate that the density of grafted chains in the interfacial layer 2–3 nm above the interface is approximately double than that of polymer chains in bulk [4].

3.6 COMPARISON WITH PNCs BASED ON THERMOPLASTIC POLYMER

Results so far demonstrate that for PNCs based on rubber-like polymers the polymer at the particle interfaces demonstrates a retarded dynamics as compared to the bulk. This dynamics is recorded through a separate segmental relaxation mechanism in DRS, while in DSC the interfacial polymer fraction is thought immobile, reducing the heat capacity change at glass transition. In this section of the manuscript we study the respective effects of the presence of various types of nanosized fillers on segmental dynamics of the PLLA thermoplastic matrix. The study is based, again, on findings by DSC (Figure 9a) and DRS (Figure 9b). We recall that PLLA is a semicrystalline polymer (X_c between 0.20 and 0.50 wt for the specific type [17]). Thus, in order to minimize any effects of crystallization, our study involves measurements on amorphous samples that have been previously quenched.

Figure 9: Effects of various nanosized fillers on the (a) calorimetric and (b) dynamic glass transition of PLLA. (c) estimated interfacial PLLA fraction against filler type, as obtained from DSC and DRS measurements at T_g and 75 °C, respectively.

Figure 9a shows comparative DSC thermograms in the temperature region of the glass transition for PLLA NCs. T_g recorded at about 60 °C for neat PLLA is almost unaffected by filler addition. At the same time the heat capacity step, ΔC_p , reduces. Employing Eq. (1), we estimate the interfacial polymer fraction, RAF_{DSC} , for the various compositions. RAF_{DSC} varies between 0.05 and 0.20 wt in Figure 9b, being lower in the case of silica/PLLA and higher for CNTs/PLLA NCs.

In Figure 9b we compare the segmental α relaxation (dynamic glass transition of bulk) at 75 °C located at around 10 kHz. In the case of silica and GO based samples, α is recorded at slightly lower frequencies (suggesting higher dielectric T_g), while in the case of Ag based sample, α is faster (lower dielectric T_g), as compared to α of neat PLLA. Simultaneously with these changes on dynamics, α relaxation decreases in strength ($\Delta \epsilon$) with filler addition. Please note that in contrast to PDMS, in the case of PLLA we did not clearly recorded any relaxation that could be referred to the mobility of PLLA at the filler/polymer interface. A possible explanation is that this is due to the lower flexibility of PLLA, in comparison with PDMS. Therefore, we assume that the interfacial polymer is immobile in DRS, similarly to DSC. Using the following equation, we estimate RAF_{DRS} as the deviation of the dielectric strength of α relaxation of the NCs from that of neat PLLA.

$$RAF_{DRS} = 1 - \Delta\epsilon_{\alpha}^{NC} / \Delta\epsilon_{\alpha}^{polymer} \quad (5)$$

RAF_{DRS} is significantly higher than RAF_{DSC} , varying between 0.10 and 0.35 wt in Figure 9c and being, again, lower for silica/PLLA and higher for CNTs/PLLA. Work is in progress for the evaluation of the real accessible (to polymer) surface area in NCs, depending on the degree of filler dispersion and aggregation in NCs.

4 CONCLUSIONS

DRS in combination with DSC revealed that the increase of filler content and the surface roughness of the inclusions (described by specific surface area, S_{BET}) results in increase of polymer–particle contact points (accessible hydroxyl groups) in the case of rubber-like polymers (PDMS). This effect is reflected in increased interfacial polymer fraction and, furthermore, enhanced mobility and cooperativity. Relaxation of the polymer at interfaces (α_{int} process) could be recorded separately from that in bulk. The characteristics of α_{int} relaxation were interpreted in terms of bimodal conformations (tail– and loop–like) of PDMS at the oxide surfaces. According to a previously proposed model [12], we suggest that during the initial adsorption of PDMS the chains are strongly attached (although sparsely distributed) and highly orientated (tails) over the surfaces, characterized by lower cooperativity. The increasing of surface roughness (S_{BET}) results in the increase of the concentration of accessible to PDMS contact points and, thus, of the number of tails. Further polymer adsorption proceeds via loop–like conformations, probably in more dense packing onto the surfaces, resulting in increase of the degree of cooperativity of polymer chains in the interfacial layer and in faster interfacial dynamics [12]. Thus, the density of interfacial polymer should increase with S_{BET} . This increase is probably related to the reported increase of mean textural pore size with S_{BET} [18], resulting in increased accessibility of the filler surface to the polymer chains. Therefore, we conclude that number and accessibility of contact points (surface properties of the particles) and structure and flexibility of polymer chain (polymer topology at the interfaces) dominate interfacial interactions. In the case of NCs based on PLLA (thermoplastic, in contrary to the rubbery PDMS), DSC and BDS revealed a suppression of bulk segmental mobility (glass transition and α relaxation, in DSC and BDS, respectively) on the addition of nanosized fillers (of various types and dimensionality). However, in the case of PLLA the existence of interfacial dynamics could not be recorded separately from that of the bulk, most probably due to the low flexibility of the PLLA chains and the significant contribution of conductivity to dielectric loss at low frequencies, as compared to PDMS, a point worth to be further investigated in future work.

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